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Filling in the blanks: Rethinking Terms of Service (ToS) through design

With the emergence of networked computational things – *fluid assemblages* – the concept of ownership has been replaced with the concept of ongoing relationships facilitated through Terms of Service (ToS) agreements (Redström and Wiltse, 2019). However, long and complex ToS with legal and technical jargon usually stands in the way of goals – tasks to be completed, information to be acquired or fun to be experienced. As a result, it is often ignored with a quick tick on the ‘I have read and agree on the ToS’ statements (Luger et al., 2013; Bakos et al., 2014; Obar and Oeldorf-Hirsch, 2018; Reinhardt et al., 2021; Taber et al., 2020; Tabassum et al., 2018). This highlights the intriguing contradiction between the complexity of ToS and simplicity of bypassing it. While ToS’s function is to clarify roles, rights, responsibilities, and practices --to get informed consent before engagement, the interaction is designed in such a ‘usable’ flow to bypass it. This contradiction makes it essential to design more meaningful ways of relating to fluid assemblages that do not cause us to lie and lose our dignity one tick at a time.

The success of human-centered design might lead us to think that extending the usability approach to ToS might solve the issue of ‘meaningful interaction’ by making things fit – ToS, user, and the system (Redström, 2006). However, the experiments of making ToS more usable – accessible, readable, and comprehensible – have shown insignificant gains in engagement and comprehensibility (Das et al., 2018; Jones et al., 2017; Kay and Terry, 2010; Kelley et al., 2009; Kelley et al., 2010; Reinhardt et al., 2021; Tabassum et al., 2018; Taber et al., 2020). Critiquing this approach, in my PhD project¹ I propose understanding ToS by moving around it and zooming in and out through the lenses of (auto)ethnography, programmatic research, and entanglement theories to see if ToS needs fixing or taking another route. Through this movement that plays with scale, I find and create blank spaces to fill in with other questions: How might we then design alternatives to ToS? What kinds of worldviews, ethical frameworks,

¹ I am conducting my PhD at Umeå Institute of Design as part of DCODE, an EU Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network (ITN). DCODE is a consortium of seven exceptional higher education institutions and stakeholders from industry, government, and civil society across Europe. Bringing together 40 researchers from 20 countries over four years, among them Technische Universiteit Delft, Københavns Universitet, Aarhus Universitet, Transport & Telecommunication Institute Lv, Stichting Hogeschool Van Amsterdam, Philips Electronics, and The University of Edinburgh, DCODE is set to rethink the digital transformation of society through 5 work packages, ‘inclusive digital futures, trusted interactions, sustainable socio-economic models, democratic data governance, and future design practices’.

methods, and practices do we need? How would these alternatives be? (DCODE, 2021). This ongoing movement shapes three unfolding practices making up my research program, aesthetics of relating: *releasing design for Terms of Trauma*, *revealing design for Terms of Entanglement*, and *reimagining design for Terms of Care*.

In *releasing design for Terms of Trauma* I deal with recognizing the problems at different scales through two experiments: (i) *ToSymphony*, and (ii) *Programmatic Time Travel*². *ToSymphony*, staying at the user level, releases the private experience of encountering ToS ecosystems over a period of time to the public realm by transposing autoethnographic data into sound expression. Transforming the silent private interactions into loud public ones not only acknowledges the psychic numbing (Zuboff, 2019) through the consistent accumulation of these interactions but also makes it a public problem rather than an individual. *Programmatic Time Travel (PTT)*, on the other hand, works at design level proposing to release design from ‘the future’ path by activating historical resources for reinterpreting contemporary concepts to find alternative paths. Through the four tactics of *PTT* as (i) *disorientate* – make associations between now and then, (ii) *trace the path* – focus on the acts not the outcomes, (iii) *turn toward past and present (recursively)* – define distinctions between now and then, (iv) *reorientate* – use connections to create a new program, I arrive at a new starting point for a design program to unfold, a reorientation other than the usability program.

In *revealing design for Terms of Entanglement*³ I reframe the everyday gestures of ignoring ToS, often referred as the biggest lie on the internet (Obar and Oeldorf-Hirsch, 2018) putting the agency, and thus, the guilt on users, as a symptom of *technological gaslighting*⁴ enabled through the practice and rhetoric of *surveillance capitalism*⁵ (Zuboff, 2019). It is based on five moves rooted in posthuman theories (Forlano, 2017; Frauenberger, 2019) and more-than-human design (Giaccardi and Redström, 2020), (i) decentering the user through *revealing use and users*, (ii) alien phenomenology through *thing therapy*, (iii) co-performance through *adjusting appropriateness*, (iv) entanglements through *relational mapping* (Figure 1), and (v) onto-cartography through *power mapping*. These moves help reveal not only the multiple nonhuman actors but also the *multiintentionality* – their intentions in relating to technology (Redström and Wiltse, 2019) and *reverse intentionality* – making use of users’ usage data in generating and leveraging insights (Wiltse, 2020) in fluid assemblages.

² Özçetin, S. and Redström, J. [Paper in progress]. Programmatic time travel: Terms of Service meets machine art.

³ Özçetin, S. and Wiltse, H. 2023. Terms of Entanglement: A posthumanist reading of Terms of Service. [Paper under review at the *Journal of Human Computer Interaction*, Special Issue: Posthumanist HCI and the More-than-human Turn in Design].

⁴ “a pattern of behavior in which technology companies are able to control significant elements of users’ worlds in combination with a narrative that creates and reinforces a sense of helplessness while simultaneously denying their own felt sense of reality” (see footnote 3 for reference).

⁵ Business model platform companies are employing that relies on revenue created by using insights generated through the use of data intensive things.

Figure 1. An unfinished *Relational Mapping* experiment of policy ecosystem of Clue, a *femtech* application. The diagram illustrates the multiple actors (users, corporations, geographical spaces, laws and regulations) and hence the additional policies one agrees to as agreeing to the ToS and PP of a single application.

In *reimagining design for Terms of Care*, I intend to explore the dimensions of an *aesthetics of relating* program through a care-centric more-than-human approach grappling with entanglements and interdependencies within the context of *femtech* and/or healthcare. I will create speculative scenarios that explore how rather care-full relationships can be formed and sustained by unpacking notions such as temporality and everyday negotiations in co-performance.

Through these practices, I propose a conceptual shift from ToS, a single policy document, to *ToSsphere*⁶, a dynamic ecosystem of policies distributed across corporations and continents, consisting of not only the policies from the service itself but also its third-party services and the local and international laws and regulations that they are bound by (Figure 1). Reframing of ToS

⁶ See footnote 1 and 2 for reference.

as *ToSphere* creates a better picture of what we are encountering. Further, I illustrate the necessity of a theoretical and methodological shift to more-than-human design.

I will collect my work exemplifying alternatives to ToS through programmatic research through design methodology (Redström, 2017) in a monograph. It will open pathways for rethinking design in digital transformation and offer insight for policymaking with the conceptual, theoretical, and methodological shifts as well as the new design practices in democratic data governance space.

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